

Spatial and Temporal Analysis of Urban Spatial Structure using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing – The Case of Nsukka, Nigeria

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Abstract

With urbanization and rapid population growth driving global urban spatial growth, the United Nations predicts that 68% of the global population would reside in urban centres by 2050. This suggests that many small-sized settlements will grow organically to accommodate the anticipated population shift and become urbanized while existing urban centres will witness spatial expansion and densification in response to the needs of their inhabitants. Using geospatial technologies of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing, this study investigates the trend and spatial pattern of urban growth in Nsukka, Southeast Nigeria, from year 2004 to 2024, and based on the trend analysis of the growth and its drivers, the settlement's growth was modelled to 2039. The results show that between 2004 and 2024, built-up areas in Nsukka increased by about 64% while vegetated land decreased by 37%. Bare land declined from a total of 9.7% to 3.1% while cultivated land increased from 88 hectares to 98 hectares. By 2039, vegetated land cover is predicted to account for less than 10% of the total land area while built-up land cover will be 65.3% of the total land area from 25% in 2004. The growth pattern suggests the need to institute both urban and economic planning strategies to support livelihoods and build mitigations against future negative consequences of the growth like congestion, waste management, pollution, food insecurity and the many health effects of climate change as a result of disappearing vegetal cover.

Keywords: Urban Growth, Densification, Geospatial Technologies, Urban Planning, Nsukka

1 Introduction

Urban centres are living organisms. They exhibit metabolism, response, adaptivity, growth and reproduction (Zhao *et al*, 2024). In this context, urban growth is seen as organic, that is, a response to the internal de-

mands and needs of the inhabitants. These include the need for the building of houses, streets, businesses, infrastructure and social services incrementally as the demands for them arise. This contrasts with the concept of planned growth where cities strictly follow a structured Master plan and other urban planning strategies to achieve walkability, mixed land-use and accessibility (Srinivas, n.d). Growth in many urban centres across the world is typified by the organic growth process. Notable examples include Paris, Tokyo, Amsterdam and Marrakech (Srinivas, n.d). The organic growth of cities is mostly underpinned by the two related factors of urbanization and rapid population growth (Korah *et al*, 2025; Angel, 2023; Adewoyin *et al*, 2020).

According to a United Nations' report, global population is currently estimated at 8.2 billion, and this is projected to rise by more than 2 billion to 10.3 billion in the next six decades (UN, 2024). The population of Nigeria, like India, Indonesia, Pakistan and the United States of America, is expected to continue growing through 2054, potentially reaching a peak later in the century or beyond 2100. The country is projected to be the 5th most populous country in the world by 2054, rising to the 4th position by 2100 (UN, 2024). With only 30% of the world population living in urban centres in 1950, the proportion rose to 55% in 2018, and is expected to be around 68% of the global population by 2050 (United Nations, 2019). This suggests that many small-sized settlements will grow organically to accommodate the anticipated population shift and become urbanized while existing

urban centres will witness spatial expansion and densification in response to the needs of their inhabitants.

While urban growth is widely acknowledged as being positively correlated with economic growth, reduction in poverty and a rise in various indices of human development (Adewoyin *et al*, 2020), the associated land use demand and land use change, and attendant anthropogenic activities, come with a myriad of planning concerns. These include congestion and overcrowding - as well as their health consequences, traffic congestion, increased energy consumption, environmental pollution, shortage of infrastructure, and damage to ecosystems. Urban planning allows for an anticipation of future growth of cities by guiding the direction and spatial pattern of growth with a view to controlling and managing the negative consequences of such growth. In relation to new cities, Elhanafy (2023) describes this strategy as guided organic growth.

A major fulcrum on which a future growth forecast would be based is an understanding of the trend of growth and the drivers of the growth over a period of time. Geospatial technologies like Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing offer a robust window into the growth history of an urban centre. They also allow for a robust modelling of the future growth of cities. The literature is replete with studies on the application of these geospatial technologies in the study of urban spatial growth, including in Nigeria (Balogun *et al*, 2011; Odjugo *et al*, 2014; Ahmed *et al*, 2024; Gilbert and Shi, 2024 for instance). In this study, we employ Nsukka, a medium-sized, fast-growing urban centre in South-East Nigeria as our study area for the application of the geospatial technologies. The study investigates the spatial growth of Nsukka from year 2004 to 2024 and based on the trend analysis of the growth and its drivers, we model the spatial expansion to 2039.

Methods

The Study Setting

Nsukka, the headquarters of Nsukka Local Government Area (LGA) in Enugu State, South-east, Nigeria, is located approximately within latitudes $6^{\circ} 48'$ and $7^{\circ} 00'$ N and longitude $7^{\circ} 20'$ and $7^{\circ} 30'$ E. It has a total landmass of 288km^2 . It is bounded by Ibagwani and Obukpa to the North, Obimo and Opi to the South, Orba to the

West, and Ikap to the East. All the listed adjoining settlements are equally embedded within Nsukka LGA. Nsukka is the northernmost major settlement in the South-East region of Nigeria. The LGA shares boundaries with Kogi State. Nsukka has an elevation of between 212 and 480m above sea level and the settlement lies within the Eastern Sedimentary basin underlain by crystalline basement complex rocks. Aside housing the University of Nigeria, a federal higher institution of learning established since 1960, other functions and attractions in Nsukka include the LGA headquarters, School of Nursing, federal establishments like the Federal Road Safety Commission and the Nigerian Police Area Command, judicial services, primary and secondary education services, recreational services,

banks and commercial activities as well as modern and traditional markets. Nsukka connects all Southeast and South-South States to Northern Nigeria, especially North-Central and North-West Nigeria, by road. Figures 1-3 show Nsukka in its national and regional settings.

Figure 1: Map of Enugu State Showing the Study Area
Source: geoBoundaries (www.geoboundaries.org)

Figure 2: Map of Nsukka LGA

Source: geoBoundaries (www.geoBoundaries.org)

Figure 3: Map of Nsukka Township

Source Authors' 2025

Data Types, Sources and Method of Collection

Both primary and secondary data were employed for the study. Satellite imageries over Nsukka were obtained for the years 2004, 2014 and 2024. The downloaded satellite images from Landsat 5, Landsat7 Thematic Mapper (TM), and Landsat 8 Enhanced Thematic Mapper (ETM+) were obtained as ortho-rectified / geo-referenced L1T (terrain corrected) products from SAS Planet and Global Land Cover Facility (GLCF). Standard Garmin 12 hand-held Global Position System (GPS) device was used for ground truthing the imageries and to obtain coordinates for geo-referencing features of interest.

Data Analysis

Consequent on a ground-truthing exercise, the coordinates of five control points from the satellite

imageries were established. A comparison of the results shows that all the data points were acceptable except for the Enhanced Thematic Mapping (ETM+) sensor scenes, from which selected points did not exactly match with the corresponding ground control points and ground features. Thus, the ETM+ scenes were corrected by using the image-to-image geo-referencing operation tool in the ERDAS IMAGINE software based on the ground control points. The Landsat8 ETM+ scenes were geo-referenced with a root mean square error of less than 0.5 pixels. Several control points were selected for geo-referencing ETM+ scene with the reference image.

The image of each year was mosaic to generate new image covering the entire study area. For this purpose, the mosaicking tool based on geo-referenced images was used. Thereafter, the ETM+ images were re-projected to the Universal Transverse Mercator grid using the nearest neighbour resembling method. Finally, subsets of the images of the study area were created using the Inquiry box (IB) and Area of interest (AOI) layer tool of ERDAS IMAGINE 2022 version. Once done with the pre-processing and features extraction, a supervised classification scheme was applied using the maximum likelihood algorithm classifier and interactive supervision in ARCGIS (version 10.7). The number of pixels in each of the identified classes was thereafter computed to determine the spatial extent of the land use and land cover (LULC) types in each of the study year. Change detection between the years, through image differencing, was determined using a threshold of reflectance and the mean deviation from the threshold.

Results and Discussion

Land Use / Land Cover Types and Trend of Growth

The results of the classification show four land use / land cover (LULC) classes. These were vegetated land, cultivated land, built-up area and bare surface. The spatial extent of each of the classes for the period covered is shown in Table 1. From the analysis, uncultivated vegetation was the highest land use / land cover class in 2004 in the study area. It accounted for 34.7% of total land area. This was followed by cultivated land (30.6%) and built-up area

(25.0%). By 2014, however, cultivated lands had increased while vegetated and bare lands had depleted in size. Conversely, built-up areas increased to 30.6% of total land area. Ten years later, in 2024, built-up areas had further increased to 41.0% of the land area while vegetated land and bare land had shrunk to 21.9% and 3.1% respectively. Cultivated land that initially increased in 2014 also declined to 34.0%.

he built-up areas were around three major clusters in 2004. These were the University of Nigeria (UNN) campus, Nsukka CBD eastwards, and the Owere-GRA axis. Cultivated lands adjoined these built-up areas while vegetal cover was widespread, with its preponderance around Ihe in the northwestern tip of the settlement. See Figure 4. The bare lands were found majorly around Nru, with a few found around Nkpunano and the UNN-CBD road.

Table 1: LULC Classes and Sizes in Nsukka (2004 – 2024)

S/N	LU / LC Class	2004 (%)	2014 (%)	2024 (%)
1	Vegetated Land	100ha (34.7)	79ha (27.4)	63ha (21.9)
2	Cultivated Land	88ha (30.6)	106ha (36.8)	98ha (34.0)
3	Built-Up Land	72ha (25.0)	88ha (30.6)	118ha (41.0)
4	Bare Land	28ha (9.7)	15ha (5.2)	9ha (3.1)
	Total	288ha (100.0)	288ha (100.0)	288ha (100.0)

Source: Authors, 2025

Figure 4: Classified Land Use/ Land Cover Map of Nsukka, 2004

Source: Authors, 2025

Figure 5: Classified Land Use/ Land Cover Map of Nsukka, 2014

Source: Authors, 2025

Figure 6: Classified Land Use/ Land Cover Map of Nsukka, 2024

Source: Authors, 2025

Drivers of Growth and Growth Pattern

With the benefit of being resident in the study area over the period of study, we identified a combination of several factors underlying the densification growth pattern observed in the results. In the first instance, the population of Nsukka has consistently been on the rise. This is due, majorly, to the rise in the student population at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Data from the university website shows that students population increased from a little over 38,000 in 2015 to more than 42,000 in 2025 (University of Nigeria, 2025). The University is the first university in the entire South-East and South-South regions of Nigeria and has produced several notable graduates who, in turn, want their wards to school at the University. While the student population is predominantly Igbo, the ethnic group of the region, majority of these students reside outside the town. The need to get their wards familiar with the culture and tradition of their people underpins many Igbo parents' decision to send their wards to school at Nsukka from as far as Lagos, Kano, Maiduguri and other parts of Nigeria.

Secondly, and related to the first point above, is the influx of many non-Igbo staff to the University. Until about 2016, the number of non-Igbo staff at the University was relatively few. This changed significantly recently to give the university a complete federal outlook in line with the federal character principle in the Nigerian constitution. The principle requires that all states of the federation (or where not achievable, all geopolitical regions instead) be represented at any federal establishment irrespective of where such an establishment is located. Post-2016 recruitments in the University adhered to this principle and many non-Igbo staff relocated to Nsukka with their families to take up residence. This, and the yearly increase in the number of students admitted in the university shot up the demand for housing in Nsukka, especially as the University could not accommodate the numbers in the staff quarters and available student hostels on campus. The University staff strength is currently estimated to be around 9,000.

The population factor became a pull factor that attracted more commercial activities to Nsukka to meet the demands of the population. In the period under study, even though, no new branches of commercial banks opened in the town, nearly all the existing branches of banks either relocated to a bigger space or built new offices for their operations. Shopping complexes and malls were built and more recreational facilities,

including clubs and lounges, were established. These activities also attracted more people to Nsukka for job opportunities. On the densification in particular, as elsewhere in southeastern Nigeria, land is very expensive. As such, developers maximize any unit of land they could afford by building multi-storey residences, especially multiple one-room and self-contained apartments. Some of these buildings contain more than 50 of such apartments.

Also, the autonomy of settlements and communities in Igboland is tied to their boundaries. Hence, any spatial growth in Nsukka could only be by densification without incursion into neighbouring settlements' territories. While there are buildings and other development activities springing up in these neighbouring settlements, as a spill-over of the development of Nsukka, they are mostly by indigenes of the settlements working in Nsukka, especially university Professors and LGA staffers. Another limiting factor to the spatial growth of the study area is its topography. The Digital Terrain Model (DTM) of Nsukka (Figure 7) indicates that the Nru axis has a high elevation ranging from 457.6m to 491.4m. This makes the area less prone to flooding when compared to the low terrain areas with an elevation of 390.6m to 424.2m as found around the UNN campus and Ihe. The high terrain areas attract more development while the concentration of run-off at the lower elevation areas make development less attractive and more expensive.

Predicted Growth

To predict the spatial growth of Nsukka from 2024 to the next 15 years, we performed an overlay analysis using the overlay toolbox available in ArcGIS (Version 10.7). The overlay map was calibrated to predict the extent of Nsukka urban for 2039 using a four-step procedure. First was the quantification of urban change between 2004 and 2024. The second step was to conduct a transition modelling between 2004 and 2014 while the third step was urban extent prediction for 2039. The validation of the output was thereafter conducted using the classified LULC for 2024 as reference data. The predicted growth, Figure 8, will have vegetated land decreasing from its current 63 hectares (21.9%) of LULC to 28 hectares (9.7%) while cultivated land will also decrease to 25% of LULC from 34%. Bare lands would have been taken over completely by development. The losses from

these three LULC types would increase the share of built-up area to 188 hectares (65.3%) while a new land cover type, exposed soil (5.2%), as a result of fallowing, or being designated for future development, would emerge around UNN, GRA and a pocket of other locations.

Conclusion

The analysis of the spatial growth of Nsukka between 2004 and 2024 shows that built-up areas in the settlement increased by about 64% while vegetated land decreased by 37%. In the next 15 years, vegetated land cover is predicted to account for less than 10% of the total land area of the study area from a baseline share of 34.7%. Conversely, built-up land cover would be 65.3% of total land area

from 25% in 2004. One implication of this growth is the need to institute both urban and economic planning strategies to support livelihoods and build mitigations against future negative consequences of the growth like congestion, waste management, pollution, food insecurity and the many health effects of climate change as a result of disappearing vegetal cover.

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